

Projection spread caused by missingness
in PCA on modern Eurasian populations:
Approx. # non-missing SNPs = 6000

**True position of individual
(Individual : Population)**

- HGDP00666 : Sardinian
- △ HGDP00879 : Russian
- × TP08 : Sicilian
- ◇ abh27 : Abkhasian
- ▽ NA13597 : Atayal
- ADR00514 : Nganasan
- * ALT-116 : Tubalar
- ◆ HGDP00213 : Pathan
- Loschbour_published.DG : WHG

Approx Geographical location

- a Caucasus
- a Middle_East
- a North_Europe
- a SouthEast_Asia
- a Uralic
- a East_Asia
- a North_Asia
- a South_Asia
- a SouthEur